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ASSESSMENT OF SEISMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY OF ORE RESERVES DEVELOPMENT BY GEOMECHANICAL AND GEOPHYSICAL METHODS

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Abstract

Introduction. Today, the development of complex-structure ore deposits in energy-disturbed massifs is characterized by a reduction in ore areas, a decrease in the metal content in the ore, deterioration of mining and geological and mining-technical conditions and an increase in environmental factors, increasing requirements for the safety of human life in the zone of influence of mining objects.

Purpose of the work. Justification of mining-technical, seismic and environmental safety of underground development of complex-structure ore deposits taking into account the geomechanical state of energy-disturbed massifs and seismic impact on protected objects. Based on the graph-analytical methods for calculating the justified parameters of drilling and blasting operations, an assessment is made of the stability of the parameters of outcrops of host rocks and filling material during their processing.

Scientific novelty. An empirical dependence for predicting the oscillation velocity from the reduced charge mass per deceleration stage for field conditions of the type $y=a \cdot b$ (a and b are coefficients depending on the seismic-acoustic properties of the rock mass and blasting conditions) is recommended. An increase in the scale of mass explosions is substantiated, which is possible due to an increase in the number of deceleration stages with a reduced charge mass per deceleration stage by borehole initiation (one borehole charge per deceleration stage).

Research methods. A systematic approach was used, which contains an analysis of the results of research and development work on the development of new technologies and technical means to ensure rational use, protection of mineral resources, the environment and the population, taking into account new instrumentation, geological surveying, geomechanical and seismic support using standard and new methods.

Result. Mining, seismic and environmental safety of ore deposit development is achieved by preserving the earth's surface from destruction, complex methods for assessing the stress state of host rocks and pillars of various purposes for their condition (geomechanical monitoring), as well as taking into account the degree of impact of seismic vibrations in the massif, their impact on underground and surface protected objects (seismic monitoring). This will improve the mining, seismic and environmental safety of work at deposits in the Republic of Kazakhstan, Ukraine, Australia, Canada and other developed mining countries of the world.

Keywords: ore deposits, underground mining, protected objects, mining, seismic and environmental safety.

1. Introduction

The studies of seismic action of explosion were carried out, in particular: in Kryvbas, Ukraine; OJSC "Poltava GOK", Ukraine; PJSC "Zaporizhzhya Iron Ore Plant" (PJSC ZZhRK), Ukraine; State Enterprise "Ukrainian Research and Design and Survey Institute of Industrial Technology" (SE "UkrNIPromtekhologii") and State Enterprise "Eastern Mining and Processing Plant" (SE "VostGOK"), Zhovti Vody, Ukraine; State Enterprise "Kirovgeologiya", Kyiv, Ukraine; National Technical Univer-

sity "Dnipro Polytechnic" and the Institute of Geotechnical Mechanics named after N.S. Polyakov of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (IGTM NASU), Dnipro, Ukraine; State Higher Educational Institution "Kryvyi Rih National University", Kryvyi Rih, Ukraine; Joint-Stock Companies "VNIPIpromtekhologii" and "VNIMI", St. Petersburg, Russia and others, where mining operations are carried out using blasting operations. The following were involved in the management of seismic action of blasts: Institute of Physics of the Earth of the USSR Academy of Sciences, JSC "UNIIPROMED", JSC

"VNIITSVET", JSC "VNIPIIpromtehnologii", JSC "NIKMA" and others. Abroad, these studies were conducted in the USA, Germany, France, Chile, Australia and other developed mining countries of the world [1, 2].

The safety of surface buildings and structures in the zone of influence of mining operations largely depends on the intensity and nature of the passage of wave processes during blasts in elastic rock massifs, which form patterns corresponding to their geomechanical and geotechnical conditions [3, 4]. In addition, the safety of structures is determined by the state of loose deposits on the surface of the crystalline foundation, the presence of waterlogging, landslides, etc. [5, 6]. These tasks can be accomplished through ongoing research into the patterns of propagation of seismic waves and the use of technological methods that reduce the volume of explosives per deceleration (intra-fan deceleration, reduction in the height of the sub-level, counter blasting with separation of the seismic wave front, screening, etc.) [7, 8].

Therefore, geophysical support for seismically safe technology for developing ore deposits in energy-disturbed massifs of complex structure using geophysical methods, taking into account mining operations schemes, rational methods for controlling rock pressure, strength and composition of the hardening backfill mixture, the order of mining ore deposits that ensure the stability of outcrops in energy-disturbed rock massifs and the preservation of the earth's surface, water bodies and residential buildings in the zone of influence of mining operations, is an important scientific, practical and social task that requires an urgent solution [9, 10]. This ensures a rational method for controlling rock pressure by using chamber systems with backfill of hardening mixtures of different compositions and strengths. This work is a continuation of research, the main scientific and practical results of which are most fully presented in [11, 12].

Research methods and terms used. The authors analyzed previously conducted studies and control observations, instrumental measurements of the seismic action of the explosion with devices and equipment, mathematical analysis and statistical processing of the results, establishment of dependencies, calculations and justifications using standard and new methods with the participation of the authors of the article under consideration.

Permissible velocity of seismic ground vibrations is the velocity at which the preservation of buildings and structures is completely guaranteed, and probable local deformations do not exceed the predicted ones.

Short-delay blasting is the sequential blasting of individual charges or individual groups of charges with predetermined time intervals measured in milliseconds.

Explosive substance (ES) is a chemical compound or mixture that is capable, under certain conditions, of a very rapid self-expanding chemical transformation with the release of heat and a large amount of gaseous products.

Blasting operations are a set of organizational and technical measures related to the preparation and implementation of blasts.

The object of the study is the technology and technical means for underground ore mining in energy-disturbed massifs of complex structure. One of the most problematic areas is the formation of man-made voids that affect the occurrence and redistribution of the stress-strain state (SSS) of the rock mass. Their existence in the earth's crust, especially during the development of near-surface reserves of rock deposits, provokes the influence of geomechanical and seismic phenomena, up to the level of earthquakes [13, 14].

The purpose of the study is geophysical support for seismically safe technology for the development of ore deposits in energy-disturbed massifs of complex structure using geophysical methods, taking into account mining operations schemes, rational methods for managing rock pressure, strength and composition of the hardening backfill mixture, and the order of ore deposit development. This will ensure the stability of outcrops in energy-disturbed mountain ranges and the preservation of the earth's surface, water bodies and residential buildings in the zone of influence of mining operations. It will also ensure the vital activity of the population living in the zone of influence of the mining region.

To achieve the stated goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

1. *To assess* the seismically safe displacement velocity, ensuring the safety of dilapidated residential buildings and reducing the negative impact of seismic explosive tremors on the population, taking into account the social factor.

2. *To develop* a graph-analytical method for determining seismically safe parameters when mining ore deposits of complex structure using chambers with backfill of different composition and strength.

3. *To establish* the mass of explosive charges with uniform distribution by deceleration stages.

4. *To recommend* empirical dependencies for predicting the oscillation velocity from the reduced mass of the explosive charge per deceleration stage for the conditions of a deposit of complex structure.

2. Material and research methods

The near-surface reserves of the Michurinskoye deposit of the State Enterprise VostGOK (Ukraine), a significant part of which lies under the Ingul River, are represented by steeply dipping ore bodies of varying thickness, along with industrial and civil buildings and structures. The length of the ore bodies is from 600 to 700 m along the strike (mainly 100–250 m), along the dip from 150 to 400 m. The ores and host rocks are strong: the hardness coefficient according to the scale of prof. M. M. Protodyakonov ($f=14-18$), massive, have a non-layered structure. Towards the surface, there is a significant deterioration in the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of fracturing both for individual deposits and for the deposit as a whole. At the upper horizons the rocks are weathered, the f coefficient decreases to 6. The deposit is developed by a chamber mining system with backfilling of the mined-out space with a hardening mixture (Fig. 1).

Mining operations are carried out at a depth of 40–50 m to 350 m. The chambers are developed in sub-floors 10–15 m high. Ore is broken by borehole charges with diameters of 57 and 65 mm, drilled by NT–2 and

PK-75 rigs. Parallel downward boreholes with diameters of 85 and 105 mm for the formation of cut-off slots are drilled by NKR-100 M rigs. The efficiency of drilling operations in mines is increased by using high-performance new-generation drilling equipment developed by industry specialists, as well as leading research centers (developed by NPK A and M and manufactured jointly with RMZ GP VostGOK, Ukraine), etc. [15, 16].

2.1. Assessment of the seismic effect of an explosion on surface objects. The complexity of blasting

operations during when conducting a clearing excavation under a city is associated with the seismic effect of an explosion on various objects, the integrity of which must be maintained throughout the entire period of deposit development. The technology of ore mining requires the preparation of large volumes of broken rock mass and improvement of the quality of blasting operations (the charge mass for the blast varies from 250 to 1050 kg, and for the delay interval – from 90 to 370 kg).

Fig. 1. The development system with sublevel drifts (a) crosscuts (b) with backfilling of the mined-out space with a hardening mixture: 1 – haulage drift; 2 – ventilation drift; 3 – collector; 4 – exit; 5 – block raiser; 6 – sublevel drift; 7 – undercut drift; 8 – hole; 9 – blasthole; 10 – broken ore; 11 – hardening backfill; c – fan of blastholes: 1...17 – numbers of blastholes; 6.0...12.5 – depth of blastholes, m; I, II, III – sequence of section blasting in the fan; l – size of the screening zone, m; A – zone of undercharging of boreholes.

Reduction of seismic impacts of explosions to acceptable levels for various city objects is achieved by limiting the mass of the simultaneously detonated explosive charge. This significantly complicates the breaking of rock mass and the organization of mining operations. Rational technology for conducting blasting operations in the specified conditions is ensured by organizing seismic monitoring of the safety of residential buildings above the mined deposit [17, 18].

3. Theory and practice of the issue

Graphic-analytical method for calculating the stability of outcrops of host rocks and the backfill mass. The geometric parameters of the system for developing sublevel drifts for ore deposits with a horizontal thickness of up to 15 m, when the length of the chamber along strike is 2 - 3 times or more greater than the width

(thickness), are given below. For operational monitoring of the stress-strain state (SSS) of the rock massif, sound measuring instruments were used, in particular, portable ones as the simplest means and methods of observation (developed by the scientific and production complex of automation and mechanics (NPK "A and M"), manufactured jointly with the mechanical repair plant (RMZ) of the State Enterprise "VostGOK", Ukraine) and others (Fig. 2).

Based on the results of full-scale tests of rock mass elements carried out at uranium deposits of Ukraine, the dependences of the frequency of elastic sounds of destruction on the magnitude of stresses σ were constructed, taking into account the safety factor (K_z), which is expressed as the ratio of the maximum (destructive) load [σ] acting on the structural element σ , or as the ratio of the ultimate strength of the material to the design stress, according to the formulas:

Fig. 2. Scheme of the sound-metric method for probing rock masses: *a* – sensor design; *b* – working diagram: 1 – sensor housing; 2 – crystal of Rochelle salt; 3 – cable; 4 – sensor; 5 – amplifier; 6 – oscilloscope; 7 – headphones

$$\sigma = a \cdot N_u^b; \quad (1)$$

$$K_3 = [\sigma] / \sigma, \quad (2)$$

where N_i – is the number of pulses per minute; a and b are, respectively, coefficients characterizing the structural and strength properties of the rock mass.

The current "Uniform Safety Rules for Blasting Operations" provide dependencies for determining seismically safe charges and distances for relatively simple conditions of charge blasting and design features of buildings constructed with a standard safety margin. For more complex blasting conditions (with repeated blasts in operational blocks), determining seismically safe charges and distances for preserving residential buildings, especially those constructed without the necessary safety margin, is only possible through special studies [19, 20]. The final result of the complex

of seismic studies is the creation of conditions for mining operations with guaranteed safety of objects during the development of the deposit, for example, by chamber systems with hardening backfill and breaking of the ore mass with fans of blast holes with a diameter of 67 mm.

With short-delay blasting, the charges in the delays are distributed evenly, except for the first and last stages, where the charges are reduced by 25-30% with a total blast mass of 612 kg and 7 delays, the mass of the charge of the first delay was 59.8 kg, and the last - 131.2 kg., with a total charge mass of 428.0 kg and four delay stages, the mass of the charge of the first delay was 201 kg, and the last - 20.6 kg. Analysis of the delay time used in short-delay blasting at the Central field (Ukraine) showed that the delay time between stages does not meet standard requirements (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Graph of decelerations by stages during short-delay blasting of explosives: 1, 2 - frequency of ground vibrations at the base of the protected building, Hz

The frequency of ground vibrations at the base of the protected building (curve 1) is $f_1 = 31$ Hz, i.e. the period of ground vibrations is 32 ms. The recommended deceleration between stage explosions should be $16 \text{ ms} < t_3 < 32 \text{ ms}$. For curve 2, the frequency of ground vibrations is $f_2 = 32$ Hz. The period of ground vibrations will be 32 ms, i.e. $15.5 \text{ ms} > t_3 < 31 \text{ ms}$. The recommended deceleration should be 20 - 25 ms. [21]. The actually established decelerations differ from the recommended ones by several times, or even tens of times. During the monitoring period of the seismic action of mass explosions, 23 events (explosions) were registered. Based on these measurements, the dependence of the vibration speed on the main parameters of the explosion and the hypocentral distance (the distance from the observation point under consideration to the focus) was found. To predict the speed of seismic vibrations, the authors used and refined the well-known formula of Professor M.A. Sadovsky [22]:

$$V = K \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt[3]{Q}}{R} \right)^n, \quad (3)$$

where V is the velocity of soil displacement, cm/s; n is the attenuation index of the surface vibration depending on the distance between the protected object

and the geometric center of the detonated charge (varies from 1 to 3); K is the index of the specific intensity of shaking, characterizing the seismicity of a given geological region and the technology of blasting operations, units; Q is the mass of the explosive charge per deceleration, kg; R – distance from the epicenter of the explosion to the point of placement of the sensor on the earth's surface, m.

Taking into account the obtained results of studies for specific mining-geological and mining-technical conditions of rock deposits in Ukraine, the authors have refined the dependence (3) of the type:

$$v = 52,434 \left(\frac{R}{\sqrt{Q}} \right)^{-1.6416}, \quad \text{cm/s} \quad (4)$$

Substituting into formula (2) the value of the permissible vibration speed for the least earthquake-resistant buildings in the development area - 0.7 cm/s, the authors have obtained a dependence between the permissible value of the charge in the slowdown stage and the seismic safety distance to the protected object:

$$R_{c,\delta} \geq 13,864 \sqrt{Q_{c,\delta}}. \quad (5)$$

This dependence for the rock deposit of the State Enterprise "VostGOK" is shown in graphic form in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Dependence of seismic-safe distance on charge mass in the slowdown stage for a deposit

Depending on the strength and the distance (r) to the nearest chamber operating simultaneously in the floor, the seismically safe mass of the charge per one deceleration (Q) is determined by the following formula:

$$Q = \left(\frac{2\sigma_{p.3} \cdot g \cdot 1000}{85 \cdot \gamma \cdot C_p} \right)^{2,34} \cdot r^3, \text{ kg}, (6)$$

where $\sigma_{p.3} = 0.1 \sigma_{сж}$ – temporary tensile strength of the fill kg/cm²; g – acceleration due to gravity; $\gamma = 2.3$ g/cm³ – fill density; C_p – propagation velocity of longitudinal waves in the fill mass, cm/sec. At = 30; 60

and 85 kg/cm²; $C_p = 22 \cdot 10^4$; $25 \cdot 10^4$ and $26 \cdot 10^4$ cm/sec, respectively.

Seismic-safe charge mass in fan-shaped boreholes located parallel to the boundary of the backfill massif in the sublevel drift mining system is determined by the formula

$$Q = \left(\frac{\sigma_{сж} \cdot g}{0,290 \cdot \gamma \cdot C_p} \right)^{1,44} \cdot r^3, \text{ kg}, (7)$$

Depending on the backfill hardening time, the distances from the last fan to the outcrop of the artificial massif are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Distance from the last fan on the block boundary to the backfill

Backfill hardening period, months.	Distance from the last fan on the block boundary to the backfill in borehole diameters
3	14–22
6	10–17
12	8–14

Based on the results of many years of research and development work in underground mining of complex structure deposits in energy-disturbed massifs, the authors propose mathematical models to substantiate seismic safety of charge mass per one deceleration. Calculations of the parameters were performed based on the following conditions: ore and host rocks are stable with medium fracturing, strength according to the prof. Protodyakonov scale is 12–18, the dip angle of deposits is greater than 50°; with an ore body thickness of 3–15 m, a sublevel drift development system is used, and with an ore body thickness greater than 15 m, sublevel orts are used. The floor height is 60 and 70 m, sublevels are 15–18 m; the order of sublevel development is bench-like, drilling of boreholes with diameters of 57 and 65 mm with ascending fans; the voids are filled with a hardening backfill with a strength of 1.5 to 6.0 MPa [22, 23].

The conducted analysis of seismic measuring devices showed that it is advisable to organize seismic monitoring in mines using a modern digital seismograph such as the Blast Mate Series III (manufactured by InstanTel, Canada) [24, 25]. It meets all the requirements for devices for long-term monitoring of the seismic effect of mass explosions and the requirements of international seismic safety standards (Fig. 4).

The objects of study were residential buildings in the village of Bolshaya Balka, Kropyvnytskyi, Ukraine, at 28 Krynychevata Street, and a building at 3 Matrosov Lane. These buildings are structurally “typical” for individual houses built in the 1950-60s of the last century. Seismic vibrations were recorded simultaneously both in the foundation soil of the building and in the building itself. Three-component seismic receivers were installed in the ground at a distance of 5 m from the wall opposite the explosion site and on the building ceiling.

As can be seen from the seismograms, the resulting movements are complex (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. BlastMate Series III seismograph. General view

The form of recording oscillations for each of the X, Y and Z components corresponds to the first periods. However, these oscillations quickly fade and become unnoticeable after 0.5-1 s. The velocities of ground oscillations reach their maximum values earlier than in the building. The form of the building's movement largely repeats the movement of the ground. The difference lies in the intensity of oscillations. The horizontal components of the ground oscillation velocity are more

than 2 times higher than the corresponding oscillation velocities of the building at the ceiling level, which indicates good shock-absorbing properties of the foundations. The value of the vertical component of the ground oscillation velocity is also higher than the corresponding oscillation velocity of the building. However, this difference is smaller. Permissible values of oscillation velocities according to the standards of countries of the world are given in Table 2.

Table 2

Permissible values of vibration speeds according to world standards

Name	Permissible vibration speed, cm/s		Frequency of ground vibrations, Hz	
	minimum	maximum	minimum	maximum
Germany	0,3	5,0	<10	>50
USA	1,25	5,0	<40	>40
Italy	0,3	5,0	<10	100
Spain	0,4	10,0	<15	>75
France	0,25	7,5	<10	>10
Portugal	0,25	6,0	<10	>40
Sweden	1,8	7,0	<40	>40
England	1,5	5,0	4	>40
Australia	0,2	2,5	<40	>40
India	0,2	2,5	<24	>24
Brazil	-	1,5	-	>40
Ukraine	0,2	5,2	<5	>20
Average	0,55	5,2	<17	>43

This device is reliable, easy to operate and has shown positive results in instrumental measurements at the Ingul mine of the State Enterprise VostGOK, Ukraine, in the zone of influence of blasting operations on residential buildings (Bolshaya Balka settlement,

Kropyvnytskyi city, Ukraine) and water bodies (the Ingul River) [30, 31]. The diagram of the installation of BlastMate Series III seismograph sensors on the surface during the development of ore deposits is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Installation diagram of BlastMate Series III seismograph sensors on the surface during mining of ore deposits: T1, T2 – measurement points; Bl.12-1 – production block

The characteristics of the explosions and the results of instrumental measurements of seismic ground vibrations at the base of the protected objects are given in Table 3. BlastMate Series III seismic devices make it possible to obtain complete information on the parameters of the seismic action of the explosion immediately after the completion of the explosion and to have a supporting document in the form of a protocol printed by a computer. The influence of the human factor, errors in processing and presenting information is excluded. During the period of monitoring the seismic action of mass explosions, 23 events (explosions) were registered. Based on these measurements, the dependence of the vibration speed on the main parameters of the explosion and the hypocentral distance (the distance from the observation point under consideration to the focus) was found [26, 27]. The dynamics of seismic vibrations of the ground at the base of the structure of private buildings along the longitudinal axis (28 Krinichevataya St.) is shown in Fig. 7.

4. Results and analysis

Environmental and seismic safety of underground mining of ore deposits is characterized by the state of the surrounding natural environment, which excludes deterioration of the ecological situation, occurrence of danger to human health. One of the sources of man-made danger is underground mining of ore deposits under protected objects, especially water and residential buildings. To assess the seismic resistance of buildings, information is needed on the material of the supporting structures of the walls and the presence of deformations in them. Assessment of the technical condition of the housing stock in the area of seismic action of explosions was first carried out in 452 residential private buildings with stove heating and 27 buildings of housing and communal services. It was established that they do not have anti-seismic reinforcements, since they are located in a zone with seismicity below 5 points.

Fig. 7. Analysis of seismic ground vibrations at the base of a building along the longitudinal axis (28 Krinichevataya St.): a – longitudinal component of the maximum ground vibration velocity 0.376 cm/s; b – longitudinal component of the maximum structure vibration velocity 0.157 cm/s; c – spectral density of the longitudinal component of the ground vibration velocity (max. at 19.5 Hz); g – spectral density of the longitudinal component of the structure vibration velocity (max. at 8.5 Hz); d – frequency response of the structure (max. at 8.5 Hz).

Characteristics of explosions and results of instrumental measurements of seismic vibrations

Operation block number	Charge weight, kg,		Length of blasted holes per deceleration, m			Deceleration interval, ms	Bore diameter, mm	Distance to the epicenter of the explosion from the measurement point, m*			Soil displacement velocity, cm/s*	Oscillation frequency, Hz*
	Total	Per deceleration interval	Total	Charged	Undercharged			Vertical	Horizontal	Resulting		
1a-2-7T	522,0	83,2	22,5	18	4,5	25	67	290,0	236,0	374,0	0,218	30,0
1б-1-1T	308,0	61,6	20,0	13,2	6,8	0	67	327,0	188,0	377,0	0,054	35,0
1б-1-1T	462,0	96,4	30,0	21,0	9,0	25	67	327,0	188,0	377,0	0,054	40,0
1a-2-1T	612,0	59,8	39,0	9,0	30,0	25	85	275,0	156,0	316,0	0,164	26,0
1a-2-7T	398,0	129,4	27,0	19,5	7,5	25	85	300,0	250,0	390,0	0,2	37,0
1a-1-1T	676,0	163,6	84,5	34,0	50,5	25	85	327,0	71,0	334,0	0,26	21,0
1a-2-1T	428,0	201,4	50,0	42,5	7,5	25	85	285,0	155,0	324,0	0,215	25,0

According to the three-point system of assessing the condition of buildings (good, satisfactory, dilapidated), about 77% of private buildings were in good and satisfactory condition and 23% were in dilapidated, deformed condition, i.e. had cracks in adobe and clay walls, gaps in load-bearing walls between window openings and had no foundations. Cracks in the upper zone of the brick cladding of the outer wall of the house at 27 Adzhamsky Lane, (Bolshaya Balka settlement, Ukraine) are shown in Fig. 8.

The state-owned buildings were in satisfactory condition. Inspection of the structures of 15 buildings in which deformations and cracks were detected showed that no increase in deformations of the inspected residential buildings was detected, and the existing deformations do not pose a danger to the buildings, provided that current repairs are carried out [28, 29].

For damaged buildings with significant cracks in the load-bearing structural elements, the permissible displacement rate is taken to be no higher than 1 cm/s, and taking into account the social factor 0.4–0.8 cm/s. Experience confirms that with a displacement rate not exceeding 1 cm/s, the population practically does not experience negative reactions to the seismic action of blasting operations carried out near residential buildings. Sometimes the psychological impact of the seismic effect depends on the state of the person. While resting, a person feels the same vibrations as more impressive than while being active. The psychological impact also increases with an increase in the period of vibrations of buildings. Therefore, when determining the permissible speed of soil displacement at the base of a protected object, it is necessary to take into account the psychological impact of seismic explosive vibrations on a person [30, 31].

a

b

c

Fig. 8. Cracks in the upper zone of the brick cladding of the outer wall of the house at 27 Adzhamsky Lane: a, b, c – crack opening width up to 4, 8 and 12 mm, respectively

As a result of conducting a set of scientific research works, the authors established a modern technical level of the applied development system, standardized its elements and technological processes, compiled a set of enterprise standards "System of development by sublevel drifts (orths) with backfilling of the mined space with a hardening mixture. Parameters and dimensions", which regulates (depending on mining and geological conditions) the length, width and height of the chambers of the first, second and third stages of extraction, their maximum permissible values, taking into account the change in the strength properties of the backfill during its hardening and the depth of development, the height of the sub-level and the bottom of the block, the distance between the discharge loading and delivery workings (holes) depending on the thickness of the ore body and the height of the level, the shape and dimensions of the cross-sections of the main side workings.

Technological parameters of the development system: the equipment used, the method and mechanization of ore release, the procedure for processing and breaking chamber reserves, the location and diameter of boreholes are also determined depending on the previously standardized parameters and dimensions of the chambers. This set of standards has been implemented in ore mines of Ukraine and is successfully used by specialists of technological and geological surveying services [32, 33].

The main safety criterion for determining the permissible parameters of ground vibrations is the permissible velocity of seismic vibrations and their frequency, at which the preservation of buildings and structures is guaranteed, and the probability of their deformation does not exceed permissible forecasts. Based on instrumental measurements of the seismic effect of an explosion in ore mines in Ukraine on residential buildings and water bodies in the zone of influence of mining operations, the following has been established [34, 35]:

- environmental safety of mineral deposit development is achieved by preserving the earth's surface from destruction, using complex methods for assessing the stress state of enclosing rocks and pillars of various purposes for their condition (geomechanical monitoring), as well as taking into account the degree of impact of

seismic vibrations in the massif and their effect on surface objects (seismic monitoring);

- inspection and assessment of the condition of more than 20 residential buildings, in which various deformations and individual cracks were detected, showed that the cause of the said deformations is insufficient strength and depth of the foundation, as well as subsidence of the structure as a result of wetting of sedimentary soils;

- it was established that the permissible seismically safe mass of the explosive charge for a delay interval of 50 and 75 ms at a distance from the explosion site to the protected object of 230 m is equal to 220 kg, and at a distance of 285 m - 490 kg, which is convincingly confirmed by the practice of developing uranium deposits.

Thus, in case of systematically repeated explosions over a long period of time, in order to preserve buildings located within the mine allotment and in the blast impact zone, the maximum permissible charges of explosives per deceleration stage must be restricted to such limits that the resulting maximum oscillation velocities would be less than those provided for by the safety standard, taking into account the oscillation frequency [36, 37]. In order to obtain comprehensive explanations of the causes of deformation of residential buildings and to control the seismically safe conduct of blasting operations, it is necessary to conduct further seismic monitoring of the intensity of seismic vibrations and deformation in the structures of protected objects in combination with research on mining and geodynamic processes in the massif [38, 39].

4.1.Promising research directions. The obtained results do not exhaust the problem of nature and resource conservation, environmental and human protection. The development of methodological foundations for optimizing mining technology should lead to the creation of an appropriate subsystem for automating the design and planning of mining operations, increasing the technological and ecological safety of the environment, rational use and protection of mineral resources, as well as the safety of human life in the zone of influence of mining operations [40, 41].

5. Conclusion

It is shown that with a seismically safe displacement velocity of 0.4 cm/s, the recommended technology made it possible to ensure the safety of dilapidated residential buildings, reduce the negative impact of seismic explosive tremors on the population, taking into account the social factor.

It is determined that when producing industrial explosions, fan charges should be placed normally to the protected objects, while the seismic impact on the object is reduced by 4 times. The method of preliminary slit formation will make it possible to significantly reduce the degree of seismic blasting effects on protected objects and increase the mass of the explosive charge in one deceleration interval from 2.7 to 5.0 times.

It was established that the mass of charges should be uniformly distributed over the deceleration stages, except for the first and last ones. The mass of the first and last stages should be 25-30% less than in the others. The number of deceleration stages should be at least 3-4.

An empirical dependence for predicting the oscillation velocity from the reduced mass of the charge per deceleration stage for field conditions of the type $y=a \cdot b$ is recommended (a and b are coefficients depending on the seismoacoustic properties of the rock mass and blasting conditions). An increase in the scale of mass explosions is possible due to an increase in the number of deceleration stages with a reduced charge mass per deceleration stage by borehole initiation (one borehole charge per deceleration stage).

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